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Social science research in Indonesia (1999–2023): Identifying hotspots and trends through bibliometrics

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Abstract

Background: The progress of social sciences in Indonesia is evident through the surge in research activities, as showcased by publications in globally respected journals. A study by Putera et al. points out that, for the first time between 2002 and 2004, Indonesian authors ranked social sciences among the top five fields with international publications. Since the 1998 reform era, the social sciences have encountered exciting opportunities and significant challenges. These challenges underscore the urgent need for further development. Significant efforts are needed to enhance the presence and impact of Indonesian social science thought globally.

Objectives: To identify hotspots and trends in research from Indonesia in social sciences from 1999 to 2023 and also to identify dominant research clusters, their alignment with the UN Sustainable Development Goals, and prevalent methodologies to serve as a guide to future research and policymaking.

Methods: We employed bibliometric analysis and VOSviewer visualization to examine articles by Indonesian authors in the Scopus database, to group the articles into clusters based on their research focus, and to examine their alignment with various SDGs.

Results: We identified five dominant research clusters: (1) climate change and environmental governance, (2) Sunda Isles and archaeological evidence, (3) urban development, (4) rural development and economic impact, and (5) empowerment and food security. Each cluster had a specific focus and relevance to different SDGs. The most cited articles predominantly used qualitative methods – particularly narrative research – whereas methods such as action research, ethnography, grounded theory, and phenomenology were underrepresented.

Conclusion: Our findings emphasize the need for continued support and diversification of research methodologies to enhance the impact of social science research in Indonesia. Future research could explore underrepresented methodologies to provide a more holistic understanding of social phenomena.

Keywords:

Bibliometric analysis, Indonesia, qualitative methods, research trends, social science research, sustainable development goals

Introduction

The advancement of social sciences in Indonesia is essential for enhancing the nation's global standing. However, ineffective reforms have led to lackluster output from Indonesian universities in social sciences.¹ Research conducted by Putera et al. indicates that social sciences have only recently emerged among the top five subject areas covered by international publications by Indonesian authors between 2002 and 2004.² Having a total of 4318 programmes of studies in the country in the social sciences places them third among Indonesian higher education disciplines – behind engineering, which boasts 5106 programmes, and education, with 6127 programmes.³ These numbers suggest that significant structural challenges prevent social sciences in Indonesia from making a more critical global impact despite the sheer number of available programmes.

It is against this background that we sought to identify hotspots and trends in research from Indonesia in social sciences since the reforms that began in 1998. We chose 1998 as the starting point because the year marked a significant shift in the social and political order in Indonesia,⁴ which ushered in an era of openness and institutional and constitutional reforms, known as the reform era.⁵ The era led to major changes in research priorities and academic output, creating new opportunities and challenges.⁶ By engaging more deeply with global knowledge production and policymaking frameworks, research in social sciences in Indonesia has the potential to make a significant mark on the international stage.

Methods

Study design and setting

We used data from the Scopus database to reveal research hotspots and trends in social science in Indonesia post the Indonesian

reform era and chose Scopus because it offers extensive coverage of abstracts and citations from global and regional journals as well as conference proceedings and books,⁷ and is known for providing comprehensive metadata on scientific articles, making it an invaluable resource for bibliometric analysis.⁸

We analysed some bibliometric parameters of the 100 most cited articles identified using Scopus. The database was searched on 11 January 2024 using the following criteria: affiliation country = Indonesia, date range = 1999 to 2023, and subject area = social sciences. The chosen fields were Article title and Abstract, which were searched for the keyword 'Indonesia', and the 'Document type' = Article, conference paper, book chapter, review, book, and note. The following notation represents our search: ((AFFILCOUNTRY(Indonesia) AND TITLE-ABS-KEY(indonesia)) AND PUBYEAR > 1998 AND PUBYEAR < 2024 AND (LIMIT-TO (SUBJAREA,"SOCI")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"cp") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"ch") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"re") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"bk") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE,"no"))).

This initial search retrieved 24,188 documents, which were then sorted by the number of times they had been cited to select the 100 most cited articles: these formed the basis for our analysis.

We analysed and visualized metadata from the 100 most cited articles at the third stage, using VOSViewer. Metadata refers to such important items of information about each article such as the title, authors, year of publication, source of publication (for example, a journal, a conference, or a book), keywords, number of citations, and affiliations of the authors. Such mapping, which is highly relevant to the field of social sciences, successfully

identified various key aspects such as document type, the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), collaboration metrics, source, publisher, All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) category, Scopus quartile, research method, data collection, and average citations per year. Among the 100 most cited works, three document types stood out: articles (91%), book (2%), and reviews (7%). This information allowed us to identify research patterns and trends and to explore the connections between various topics in social sciences studied in Indonesia starting from the reforms era. The analysis therefore enabled a deeper understanding of the contributions by these articles and their impact on the social sciences.

To identify and analyse the most frequently used keywords, we extracted a total of 932 keywords (assigned to the articles by their authors) from the 100 most cited articles and then chose only those keywords that occurred at least three times. This left us with 80 keywords.

Ethics statement

Because the study involved no living entities, neither approval by the institutional review board nor informed consent was required.

Statistical methods

We used simple descriptive statistics.

Results

Supplementary Table 1 presents the mapping of the 100 most cited articles in the field of social sciences from Indonesia, using data from Scopus, for the period 1999–2023.

Document type and year of publication

Compared to other periods, the period 2014–2018 proved to be the most productive (Table 1).

Collaboration

To gain insights into the patterns of collaboration in writing academic papers, we grouped the articles into four clusters: single authorship, institutional collaboration, national collaboration, and international collaboration. Authors from Indonesia collaborated with peers from 42 countries, showing a truly international partnership (Figure 1). Moreover, Table 1 underscores Australia as the leading collaborator, accounting for 22 of the 100 most cited articles, followed by the United States (19 articles) and the United Kingdom (14 articles).

Most productive and impactful sources: publisher

The 100 most cited articles from Indonesia on social sciences were published in 58 sources (56 journals and 2 books) (Supplementary Table 2). *World Development* was at the top among the 56 contributing journals and featured 9 of the 100 articles, followed by *Global Environmental Change* (6 articles), *Forest Policy and Economics*, *Journal of Human Evolution*, and *Land Use Policy* (5 articles each). However, the most cited journal was the *Nature Climate Change*, with 602.5 citations per paper (CPP), followed by *Progress in Disaster Science* (512 CPP), *Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies* (377 CPP), *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* (342 CPP), and *Annals of Tourism Research* (297 CPP). Table 2 lists the top 10 journals in terms of the number of articles, CPP, and source normalized impact per paper (in 2023).

A total of 17 publishers accounted for the 100 most cited articles (Supplementary Table 3), with Elsevier at the top (53 articles), followed by Springer Nature (13 articles) and Taylor & Francis (9 articles). However, the most cited publisher was Florida Gulf Coast University (377 CPP), a significant finding that piques curiosity. It was followed by Modestum Ltd (342 CPP), and Cambridge University Press

Table 1. Analysis of the 100 most cited articles in social sciences from Indonesia during the period 1999–2023 as retrieved from Scopus

	Number	%
1 Document type		
Article	91	91
Book	2	2
Review	7	7
2 Publication period		
1999–2003	6	6
2004–2008	13	13
2009–2013	18	18
2014–2018	44	44
2019–2023	19	19
3 Collaboration metrics		
Single authorship	9	9
Institutional collaboration	15	15
National collaboration	5	5
International collaboration	71	71
4 Top 10 collaborating countries		
Australia	22	15
United States	19	13
United Kingdom	14	10
Japan	10	7
Netherlands	10	7
Germany	8	5
Philippines	7	5
Canada	4	3
Malaysia	4	3
France	3	2
5 UN Sustainable Development Goal		
Goal 1: No poverty	5	5
Goal 2: Zero hunger	6	6
Goal 3: Good health and well-being	12	12
Goal 4: Quality education	2	2
Goal 5: Gender equality	1	1
Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation	2	2
Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	3	3
Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	12	12
Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	5	5
Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	5	5
Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	8	8
Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	5	5
Goal 13: Climate action	9	9
Goal 14: Life below water	1	1
Goal 15: Life on land	7	7
Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	4	4
Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	13	13

(Continued)

Table 1. Analysis of the 100 most cited articles in social sciences from Indonesia during the period 1999–2023 as retrieved from Scopus (Continued)

	Number	%
6 Research method		
Mixed methods	15	15
Qualitative: Action research	1	1
Qualitative: Ethnographic	3	3
Qualitative: Grounded theory	3	3
Qualitative: Narrative research	25	26
Qualitative: Phenomenological	1	1
Qualitative: Case study	19	19
Quantitative: Survey research	14	14
Quantitative: Experimental research	17	17

(197 CPP). Table 3 lists the top five publishers in terms of the number of articles, CPP, total citations, and the number of sources.

Most cited articles

Figure 2 and Table 4 present the top 10 of the 100 most cited articles by the year of their publication, 2017 being the most productive year (13% of the articles), followed by 2014 (11%) and 2016 and 2020 (10% each).

These (the top 100 most cited) articles are highly relevant to current global issues. The most cited article, titled ‘Primary forest cover loss in Indonesia over 2000–2012’, with 693 citations, is a timely contribution, followed

by two more, titled ‘Review and analysis of current responses to COVID-19 in Indonesia: Period of January to March 2020’ and ‘The potential of Indonesian mangrove forests for global climate change mitigation’. However, in terms of the average citations per year, the first of the two appears the most impactful, followed by two other, titled ‘The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia’ and ‘Secondary school mathematics teachers’ views on e-learning implementation barriers during the COVID-19 pandemic: The case of Indonesia’.

Figure 1. International collaboration in research in social sciences involving authors from Indonesia.

Table 2. Top 10 journals that published most of the 100 most cited papers from Indonesia on social sciences and some metrics of those papers

	Source journal	TP	TC	CPP	SNIP 2023		Source journal	TP	TC	CPP	SNIP 2023
1	Top 10 by number of papers					2	Top 10 by citations per paper				
1	<i>World Development</i>	9	1207	134	2.412	1	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	2	1205	602	5.887
2	<i>Global Environmental Change</i>	6	798	133	2.605	2	<i>Progress in Disaster Science</i>	1	512	512	1.735
3	<i>Land Use Policy</i>	5	656	131	1.894	3	<i>Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies</i>	1	377	377	0.943
4	<i>Forest Policy and Economics</i>	5	608	122	1.384	4	<i>Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education</i>	1	342	342	1.079
5	<i>Journal of Human Evolution</i>	5	558	112	1.078	5	<i>Annals of Tourism Research</i>	1	297	297	2.667
6	<i>Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity</i>	3	555	185	1.646	6	<i>BMC Medical Education</i>	1	284	284	1.603
7	<i>Human Ecology</i>	3	485	162	0.762	7	<i>Landscape and Urban Planning</i>	1	205	205	2.187
8	<i>Habitat International</i>	3	438	146	1.908	8	<i>Ageing and Society</i>	1	197	197	1.547
9	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	2	1205	602	5.887	9	<i>Building and Environment</i>	2	386	193	2.022
10	<i>Building and Environment</i>	2	386	193	2.022	10	<i>Food Policy</i>	1	191	191	2.048
3	Top 10 by total citations					4	Top 10 by source normalized impact per paper (2023)				
1	<i>World Development</i>	9	1207	134	2.412	1	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	2	1205	602	5.887
2	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	2	1205	602	5.887	2	<i>Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change</i>	1	112	112	3.801
3	<i>Global Environmental Change</i>	6	798	133	2.605	3	<i>Comparative Political Studies</i>	1	110	110	3.121
4	<i>Land Use Policy</i>	5	656	131	1.894	4	<i>Journal of Peasant Studies</i>	2	285	142	3.037
5	<i>Forest Policy and Economics</i>	5	608	122	1.384	5	<i>Journal of Sustainable Tourism</i>	1	133	133	2.949
6	<i>Journal of Human Evolution</i>	5	558	112	1.078	6	<i>Journal of Business Ethics</i>	1	107	107	2.841
7	<i>Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity</i>	3	555	185	1.646	7	<i>Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies</i>	2	261	130	2.743
8	<i>Progress in Disaster Science</i>	1	512	512	1.735	8	<i>Annals of Tourism Research</i>	1	297	297	2.667
9	<i>Human Ecology</i>	3	485	161	0.762	9	<i>Environmental Politics</i>	1	102	102	2.665
10	<i>Habitat International</i>	3	438	146	1.908	10	<i>Global Environmental Change</i>	6	798	133	2.605

CPP: citations per paper; SNIP: source normalized impact per paper (2023); TC: total citations; TP: total papers.

Table 3. Top five publishers that published most of the 100 most cited papers from Indonesia on social sciences and some metrics of those publishers

Name of the publisher					Name of the publisher						
	TP	TS	TC	CPP		TP	TS	TC	CPP		
1 Ranked by number of papers					2 Ranked by citations per paper						
1	Elsevier	53	20	7893	7.45	1	Florida Gulf Coast University	1	1	377	377
2	Springer Nature	13	10	2879	22.15	2	Modestum LTD	1	1	342	342
3	Taylor & Francis	9	7	1177	18.68	3	Cambridge University Press	1	1	197	197
4	John Wiley & Sons	4	4	442	27.63	4	Society for Research and Knowledge Management	1	1	140	140
5	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	4	3	501	41.75	5	Commonwealth Forestry Association	2	1	273	136.50
3 Ranked by total citations					4 Ranked by number of source title (journal)						
1	Elsevier	53	20	7893	7.45	1	Elsevier	53	20	7893	7.45
2	Springer Nature	13	10	2879	22.15	2	Springer Nature	13	10	2879	22.15
3	Taylor & Francis	9	7	1177	18.68	3	Taylor & Francis	9	7	1177	18.68
4	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	4	3	501	41.75	4	John Wiley & Sons	4	4	442	27.63
5	John Wiley & Sons	4	4	442	27.63	5	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	4	3	501	41.75

CPP: citations per paper; TC: Total citations; TP: Total papers; TS: Total sources.

Figure 2. Distribution of the 100 most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by the year of publication and the total number of citations: 1999–2023. Note: The numbers in the boxes indicate the ranking within the top 100 most cited articles.

Distribution by subject and co-occurrence of keywords

The keywords supplied by the authors of the top 100 articles formed six clusters, each with several significant nodes (Figure 3).

Amongst the top 100 most cited articles, the largest proportion (27.5%) was of papers on geography, planning and development, followed by those on sociology and political science (21.4%), and education (9.2%). In terms of citations per paper, papers in the social sciences (miscellaneous) topped the list with 602.5 citations whereas papers on geography, planning and development earned the fewest (9.5 citations) (Supplementary Table 4).

Discussion

Nearly 3 decades of research in the social sciences have unfolded since Indonesia's era of reforms that started in 1998. That research, represented here by the top 100 most cited articles, highlights the main areas of social science research in Indonesia. Each of those papers relates to one or more of the UN SDGs and together, those papers, which formed five clusters (Figure 3), offer a comprehensive overview of the country's research landscape.

Cluster 1 focuses on climate change and environmental governance, and also includes deforestation and forestry. The cluster aligns with SDG 13 (Climate Action), SDG 15 (Life on Land), and SDG 16 (Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions), contributing insights and solutions to Indonesia's environmental challenges.^{9,19,20}

Cluster 2, Sunda Isles and archaeological evidence, explores archaeological findings, skeletal remains, and human history in the Sunda Isles and relates to SDG 15 (Life on Land), SDG 14 (Life Below Water), and SDG 4 (Quality Education), bridging the past and the present through archaeological research and education.²¹⁻²³

Cluster 3 concentrates on urban development, addressing urbanization, urban development, and decentralization in Asia. This cluster connects to SDG 11 (Sustainable Cities and Communities), SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), and SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), encompassing urban health impacts and research on COVID-19.^{10,12,15,24}

Cluster 4 examines rural development and economic impact, especially that of cultivation of oil palm, and aligns with SDG 8 (Decent Work

Table 4. Top 10 of 100 most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023. *Note:* All articles were published in journals listed in the top quartile (Q1) of journals covered in Scopus

Rank	Documents	Journal	Publisher	Year	Total citations	Total citations (excluding self-citations)	Average citations per year
1	Primary forest cover loss in Indonesia over 2000–2012 ⁹	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	Springer Nature	2014	693	644	71.56
2	Review and analysis of current responses to COVID-19 in Indonesia: Period of January to March 2020 ¹⁰	<i>Progress in Disaster Science</i>	Elsevier	2020	512	475	158.33
3	The potential of Indonesian mangrove forests for global climate change mitigation ¹¹	<i>Nature Climate Change</i>	Springer Nature	2015	512	434	54.25
4	The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the COVID-19 pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia ¹²	<i>Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies</i>	Florida Gulf Coast University	2020	377	327	109.00
5	Secondary school mathematics teachers' views on e-learning implementation barriers during the COVID-19 pandemic: The case of Indonesia ¹³	<i>Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education</i>	Modestum Ltd	2020	342	318	106.00
6	Identifying digital transformation paths in the business model of SMEs during the COVID-19 pandemic ¹⁴	<i>Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity</i>	Elsevier	2020	305	248	82.67
7	Business resilience in times of growth and crisis ¹⁵	<i>Annals of Tourism Research</i>	Elsevier	2015	297	246	30.75
8	Student perspective of classroom and distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the undergraduate dental study program Universitas Indonesia ¹⁶	<i>BMC Medical Education</i>	Springer Nature	2020	284	249	83.00
9	Process for integrating local and indigenous knowledge with science for hydro-meteorological disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation in coastal and small island communities ¹⁷	<i>International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction</i>	Elsevier	2014	228	210	23.22
10	Policies, political-economy, and swidden in southeast Asia ¹⁸	<i>Human Ecology</i>	Springer Nature	2009	233	217	15.50

Figure 3. Clustering of keywords from the top 100 most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences.

and Economic Growth), SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production), SDG 1 (No Poverty), and SDG 2 (Zero Hunger).^{18,25-27}

Cluster 5 addresses empowerment and food security, including topics on empowerment, food security, and impacts of COVID-19,²⁸⁻³⁰ and cluster relates to SDG 1 (No Poverty), SDG 2 (Zero Hunger), SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), SDG 5 (Gender Equality), and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities).

Our analysis of the 100 most cited social science articles from Indonesia (during 1999–2023) reveals a predominance of qualitative research methods. Narrative research leads, at 26%, followed by qualitative case studies (19%), quantitative experimental research (17%), mixed methods (15%), and quantitative survey research (14%). These methods, involving in-depth data collection and analysis, focus on lived experiences and social contexts and are

commonly employed to understand complex social phenomena. On the other hand, qualitative action research, ethnography, grounded theory, and phenomenology were underrepresented in the set of 100 papers and remain largely unexplored, probably because they are complex and require larger and varied resources requirements or simply because the more common methods were more suitable for the topics covered by the 100 papers.

The analysis of research hotspots and trends in research in the social sciences in Indonesia highlights the region’s diverse and dynamic academic landscape. Key focus areas are climate change and environmental governance, urban and rural development, and the socio-economic impacts of oil palm cultivation and decentralization policies. The prominence of clusters related to empowerment and food security – particularly in the context of

the COVID-19 pandemic – underscores the urgent need to address issues of inequality and sustainable development. This emphasis reinforces the importance of ongoing research in these critical areas.

This study had several limitations. First, it relied solely on one database, namely Scopus, as the primary data source. Although Scopus offers extensive coverage, limiting the search to a single database may exclude articles published in sources not indexed by Scopus or covered by other databases such as Web of Science, potentially limiting the comprehensiveness of the findings. Second, the study was restricted to the period 1999–2023, thereby focusing on more recent trends and excluding older research that could provide a broader historical context. Third, the focus on highly cited articles meant that lesser known or niche research was probably underrepresented, creating a bias towards more popular topics that might not entirely reflect the entire landscape of social science research. Fourth, the study highlighted the predominance of qualitative methods in highly cited articles, whereas quantitative methods and less represented approaches, such as action research and ethnography, remain underexplored, although they could provide more comprehensive insights. These shortcomings underline the potential for future research to delve deeper into these areas, offering more comprehensive insights and sparking curiosity in the field of social sciences.

The study reveals a strong alignment with several UN SDGs, indicating that that research is contributing significantly to the global development agenda. Notably, there is a strong emphasis on SDGs related to climate action, life on land, and reduced inequalities, reflecting the critical challenges faced by Indonesia. This alignment underscores the impact and relevance of the research to both local and global concerns. Policymakers, stakeholders,

publishers, and editors are in a unique position to enhance the impact of research related to SDGs. Additionally, the development of social sciences in Indonesia faces global challenges, as highlighted by Lad et al. (2024), who note a significant lack of awareness and resources for effectively integrating global development frameworks, such as the UN SDGs, into research and academic practices.³¹ Alarmingly, only 22% of the journals have become signatories to the SDG Publishers Compact, with many smaller journals struggling owing to limited resources and a lack of understanding of sustainability policies.

The situation calls for immediate action. Policymakers should prioritize funding and institutional support to research that aligns with the SDGs, creating incentives for interdisciplinary and collaborative studies. Stakeholders such as academic institutions and funding bodies can foster greater awareness and engagement with SDGs by incorporating them into research projects and adding them to the criteria used for judging applications for grants. Publishers and editors, on the other hand, can actively promote SDG-related research by encouraging submissions on these topics and supporting initiatives such as the SDG Publishers Compact. This multi-stakeholder approach, with its sense of urgency, will help drive the progress towards achieving the SDGs.³¹

Mapping highly cited articles has yielded valuable insights into the current state and evolution of social science research in Indonesia. These findings can guide future research directions and policymaking, aiming to foster a more inclusive, sustainable, and resilient society. The results highlight the importance of continued support to social science research to address local and global challenges effectively, reinforcing the need for ongoing inquiry and keeping stakeholders focused on future developments.

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
1	Primary forest cover loss in Indonesia over 2000-2012	Review	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Nature Climate Change	Springer Nature	Social Sciences (miscellaneous)	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Interviews; observation; Secondary Data Research	2014	693	69.30
2	Review and analysis of current responses to COVID-19 in Indonesia: Period of January to March 2020	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Progress in Disaster Science	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	rapid analysis based on media content analysis	2020	512	128.00
3	The potential of Indonesian mangrove forests for global climate change mitigation	Article	Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation	International collaboration	Nature Climate Change	Springer Nature	Social Sciences (miscellaneous)	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	observation; Secondary Data Research	2015	512	56.89
4	The perceptions of primary school teachers of online learning during the covid-19 pandemic period: A case study in Indonesia	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	Only national collaboration	Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies	Florida Gulf Coast University	Cultural Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Interviews	2020	377	94.25
5	Secondary school mathematics teachers' views on e-learning implementation barriers during the COVID-19 pandemic: The case of Indonesia	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education	Modestum LTD	Education	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	online questionnaire	2020	342	85.50
6	Identifying digital transformation paths in the business model of SMEs during the covid-19 pandemic	Article	Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Only institutional collaboration	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Interviews; observation	2020	305	76.25
7	Business resilience in times of growth and crisis	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	International collaboration	Annals of Tourism Research	Elsevier	Tourism, Leisure and Hospitality Management	Q1	Qualitative: Ethnographic	longitudinal study	2015	297	33.00
8	Student perspective of classroom and distance learning during COVID-19 pandemic in the undergraduate dental study program Universitas Indonesia	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	Only institutional collaboration	BMC Medical Education	Springer Nature	Education	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	online questionnaire	2020	284	71.00
9	Policies, political-economy, and Swidden in southeast asia	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Human Ecology	Springer Nature	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Secondary Data Research	2009	233	15.53

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
10	Process for integrating local and indigenous knowledge with science for hydro-meteorological disaster risk reduction and climate change adaptation in coastal and small island communities	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	International collaboration	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Action research	observations; focus group discussions (FGDs); semi-structured interviews; participatory mapping	2014	228	22.80
11	Multi-level governance and power in climate change policy networks	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Interviews; observation	2019	216	43.20
12	Field study on adaptive thermal comfort in office buildings in Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, and Japan during hot and humid season	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	International collaboration	Building and Environment	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Secondary Data Research	2016	205	25.63
13	Using scenarios to make decisions about the future: Anticipatory learning for the adaptive co-management of community forests	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	Only institutional collaboration	Landscape and Urban Planning	Elsevier	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Secondary Data Research	2000	205	8.54
14	A framework for understanding old-age vulnerabilities	Review	Goal 1: No poverty	International collaboration	Ageing and Society	Cambridge University Press	Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2006	197	10.94
15	Governance Failure: Rethinking the Institutional Dimensions of Urban Water Supply to Poor Households	Article	Goal 6: Clean water and sanitation	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Mixed Methods	survey; archives; GIS-based mapping; interviews	2008	197	12.31
16	Women's empowerment and gender equity in agriculture: A different perspective from Southeast Asia	Article	Goal 5: Gender equality	International collaboration	Food Policy	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	focus group discussions (FGDs)	2017	191	27.29
17	Swimming Upstream: Local Indonesian Production Networks in "Globalized" Palm Oil Production	Article	Goal 1: No poverty	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Interviews; observation	2012	189	15.75
18	Fish wars: Conflict and collaboration in fisheries management in Southeast Asia	Article	Goal 14: Life below water	International collaboration	Marine Policy	Elsevier	Law	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Interviews; observation; Secondary Data Research	2007	181	10.65

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
19	Report on thermal comfort and building energy studies in Jakarta - Indonesia	Article	Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Building and Environment	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2000	181	7.54
20	A historical analysis of the drivers of loss and degradation of Indonesia's mangroves	Article	Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	International collaboration	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2016	179	22.38
21	Illegal logging, collusive corruption and fragmented governments in Kalimantan, Indonesia	Article	Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	International collaboration	International Forestry Review	Commonwealth Forestry Association	Geography, Planning and Development	Q2	Qualitative: Single Case Study	rapid rural appraisal; semi-structured interviews	2003	170	8.10
22	Tourist loyalty in creative tourism: the role of experience quality, value, satisfaction, and motivation	Article	Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	International collaboration	Current Issues in Tourism	Taylor & Francis	Tourism, Leisure and Hospitality Management	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2020	170	42.50
23	Examining university students' behavioral intention to use e-learning during the COVID-19 pandemic: An extended TAM model	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Education and Information Technologies	Springer Nature	Education	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	online questionnaire	2021	169	56.33
24	How are REDD+ Proponents Addressing Tenure Problems? Evidence from Brazil, Cameroon, Tanzania, Indonesia, and Vietnam	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Interviews; observation; Secondary Data Research	2014	168	16.80
25	The continuity and change in mega-urbanization in Indonesia: A survey of Jakarta-Bandung Region (JBR) development	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Habitat International	Elsevier	Urban Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2009	163	10.87
26	Performance of frequency ratio and logistic regression model in creating GIS based landslides susceptibility map at Lompobattang Mountain, Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Geoenvironmental Disasters	Springer Nature	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Secondary Data Research; statistik Frequency Ratio (FR) dan Logistic Regression	2016	160	20.00
27	New town development in Jakarta Metropolitan Region: A perspective of spatial segregation	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Habitat International	Elsevier	Urban Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2004	159	7.95
28	Gendered experiences of dispossession: Oil palm expansion in a Dayak Hibun community in West Kalimantan	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Journal of Peasant Studies	Taylor & Francis	Cultural Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Grounded Theory	observation	2012	152	12.67

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
29	Fire, people and pixels: Linking social science and remote sensing to understand underlying causes and impacts of fires in Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Human Ecology	Springer Nature	Arts and Humanities	Q1	Mixed Methods	remote sensing data; hot spot data; interviews; participatory sketchmapping; and baseline information	2005	150	7.89
30	Teachers and their implementation of differentiated instruction in the classroom	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Teaching and Teacher Education	Elsevier	Education	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2017	148	21.14
31	Poverty and protected areas: An evaluation of a marine integrated conservation and development project in Indonesia	Article	Goal 1: No poverty	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Ethnographic	Longitudinal studies; observation	2014	147	14.70
32	An overview of forest and land allocation policies in Indonesia: Is the current framework sufficient to meet the needs of REDD+?	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Forest Policy and Economics	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2012	144	12.00
33	Fire economy and actor network of forest and land fires in Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Forest Policy and Economics	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Interviews; observation; Secondary Data Research	2017	144	20.57
34	Indonesia in the Time of Covid-19	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies	Taylor & Francis	Economics and Econometrics	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2020	142	35.50
35	Work from home: Measuring satisfaction between work–life balance and work stress during the covid-19 pandemic in indonesia	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	Only national collaboration	Economics	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	Economics, Econometrics and Finance (miscellaneous)	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Secondary Data Research; online questionnaire	2021	140	46.67
36	The emergency remote learning experience of university students in Indonesia amidst the COVID-19 crisis	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	Single authorship (no collaboration)	International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research	Society for Research and Knowledge Management Society for Research and Knowledge Management	Education	Q2	Qualitative: Phenomenological	Interviews; observation	2020	140	35.00
37	Prediction of land use and land cover changes for North Sumatra, Indonesia, using an artificial-neural-network-based cellular automaton	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Sustainability (Switzerland)	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Artificial-Neural-Network-Based Cellular Automaton Model	2019	139	27.80

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
38	Factors affecting customer satisfaction and loyalty in online food delivery service during the COVID-19 pandemic: Its relation with open innovation	Article	Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	International collaboration	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	Elsevier	General Economics, Econometrics and Finance	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	online questionnaire	2021	138	46.00
39	Improving junior high schools' critical thinking skills based on test three different models of learning	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	Only institutional collaboration	International Journal of Instruction	Gate Association for Teaching and Education	Education	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	mind map model; test score	2017	135	19.29
40	Oil Palm Adoption, Household Welfare, and Nutrition Among Smallholder Farmers in Indonesia	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Survey Data Collection; Econometric Models; Impact Pathways Analysis	2017	135	19.29
41	Trajectories of land acquisition and enclosure: Development schemes, virtual land grabs, and green acquisitions in Indonesia's Outer Islands	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	Only institutional collaboration	Journal of Peasant Studies	Taylor & Francis	Cultural Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	observation; Secondary Data Research	2012	133	11.08
42	Inhibitors to host community participation in sustainable tourism development in developing countries	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	Only institutional collaboration	Journal of Sustainable Tourism	Taylor & Francis	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Mixed Methods	in-depth interviews; qualitative questionnaires; observations	2014	133	13.30
43	Doctor-patient communication in Southeast Asia: A different culture?	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Advances in Health Sciences Education	Springer Nature	Education	Q1	Qualitative: Grounded Theory	in-depth interviews	2013	131	11.91
44	Developing a resilience index towards natural disasters in Indonesia	Article	Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Only institutional collaboration	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Grounded Theory	in-depth interviews	2014	131	13.10
45	Age and biostatigraphic significance of the Punung Rainforest Fauna, East Java, Indonesia, and implications for Pongo and Homo	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Journal of Human Evolution	Elsevier	Anthropology	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Geochronological method	2007	130	7.65
46	User satisfaction with paratransit in competition with motorization in indonesia: Anticipation of future implications	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	International collaboration	Transportation	Springer Nature	Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	cross-sectional survey	2007	129	7.59
47	Rural to urban land conversion in Indonesia during boom and bust periods	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	observation; Secondary Data Research	2000	128	5.33

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
48	Living close to forests enhances people's perception of ecosystem services in a forest-agricultural landscape of West Java, Indonesia	Article	Goal 1: No poverty	International collaboration	Ecosystem Services	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	interviews; Secondary Data Research	2014	127	12.70
49	Challenging the secular state: The Islamization of law in modern Indonesia	Book	Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Challenging The Secular State: The Islamization of Law in Modern Indonesia	University of Hawai'i Press	NA	NA	NA	NA	2008	124	7.75
50	The Liang Bua faunal remains: a 95 kyr. sequence from Flores, East Indonesia	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Journal of Human Evolution	Elsevier	Anthropology	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Ekskavasi Arkeologis	2009	122	8.13
51	History of forest loss and degradation in Indonesia	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Secondary Data Research	2016	121	15.13
52	Climate policy integration in the land use sector: Mitigation, adaptation and sustainable development linkages	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	International collaboration	Environmental Science and Policy	Elsevier	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	interviews; Secondary Data Research	2017	121	17.29
53	Framing the application of adaptation pathways for rural livelihoods and global change in eastern Indonesian islands	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	interviews and focus groups with local stakeholders	2014	120	12.00
54	Islam and the state in Indonesia	Book	Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Islam and the State in Indonesia	ISEAS / Ohio University Press	NA	NA	NA	NA	2003	120	5.71
55	Carbon storage and release in Indonesian peatlands since the last deglaciation	Review	Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	International collaboration	Quaternary Science Reviews	Elsevier	Archeology	Q1	Mixed Methods	Geospatial Approach; Paleogeographic Data	2014	120	12.00
56	Unity in diversity? The creation of new local governments in a decentralizing Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	Only institutional collaboration	Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies	Taylor & Francis	Economics and Econometrics	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Exploratory Approach	2005	119	6.26
57	The Economics of Kappaphycus Seaweed Cultivation in Developing Countries: A Comparative Analysis of Farming Systems	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Aquaculture, Economics and Management	Taylor & Francis	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2015	119	13.22
58	Beyond property: Industrial estates and post-suburban transformation in Jakarta Metropolitan Region	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	Only institutional collaboration	Cities	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Secondary Data Research	2012	117	9.75

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
59	Oscillations in the southern extent of the Indo-Pacific Warm Pool during the mid-Holocene	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Quaternary Science Reviews	Elsevier	Archeology	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	paleoclimatology; Geochemical Analysis	2009	117	7.80
60	Peri-urban transformation in the Jakarta metropolitan area	Article	Goal 11: Sustainable cities and communities	Only institutional collaboration	Habitat International	Elsevier	Urban Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2015	116	12.89
61	The fragmented land use administration in Indonesia - Analyzing bureaucratic responsibilities influencing tropical rainforest transformation systems	Article	Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	International collaboration	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research; Expert-Based Analysis	2015	116	12.89
62	Community forest management in Indonesia: Avoided deforestation in the context of anthropogenic and climate complexities	Article	Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Secondary Data Research; spatial matching approach	2017	115	16.43
63	Claiming the grounds for reform: Agrarian and environmental movements in Indonesia	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Journal of Agrarian Change	John Wiley & Sons	Archeology	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2008	115	7.19
64	REDD+ as Result-based Aid: General Lessons and Bilateral Agreements of Norway	Article	Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Review of Development Economics	John Wiley & Sons	Development	Q2	Mixed Methods	observation; Secondary Data Research; model simulations	2017	114	16.29
65	Transnational families and the family nexus: Perspectives of Indonesian and Filipino children left behind by migrant parent(s)	Article	Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	International collaboration	Environment and Planning A	SAGE	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2012	114	9.50
66	Improving creative thinking skills of students through Differentiated Science Inquiry integrated with mind map	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	Only national collaboration	Journal of Turkish Science Education	Ekip Buro Makineleri A.S.	Education	Q2	Quantitative: experimental research	random sampling method	2017	113	16.14
67	Tambora 1815 as a test case for high impact volcanic eruptions: Earth system effects	Review	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change	John Wiley & Sons	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Secondary Data Research; model simulations	2016	112	14.00
68	Unpacking Indonesia's independent oil palm smallholders: An actor-disaggregated approach to identifying environmental and social performance challenges	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	International collaboration	Land Use Policy	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire: interviews	2017	112	16.00

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
69	Economic growth, increasing productivity of SMEs, and open innovation	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	Only national collaboration	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	General Economics, Econometrics and Finance	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	observations, surveys, in-depth interviews	2021	112	37.33
70	Governing the design of national REDD +: An analysis of the power of agency	Article	Goal 13: Climate action	International collaboration	Forest Policy and Economics	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Semi-structured interviews; Secondary Data Research: model simulations	2014	111	11.10
71	Leadership, party, and religion: Explaining voting behavior in Indonesia	Article	Goal 16: Peace, justice and strong institutions	International collaboration	Comparative Political Studies	SAGE	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire: interviews	2007	110	6.47
72	The investigation of consumers' behavior intention in using green skincare products: A pro-environmental behavior model approach	Article	Goal 9: Industry, innovation and infrastructure	International collaboration	Sustainability (Switzerland)	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2018	110	18.33
73	Does oil palm agriculture help alleviate poverty? A multidimensional counterfactual assessment of oil palm development in Indonesia	Article	Goal 1: No poverty	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Single Case Study	Secondary Data Research	2019	109	21.80
74	Political policy for the development of education	Article	Goal 4: Quality education	Only national collaboration	International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research	Amazedia Solutions	Management of Technology and Innovation	coverage discontinued in Scopus	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2019	109	21.80
75	Tropical forest susceptibility to and risk of fire under changing climate: A review of fire nature, policy and institutions in Indonesia	Review	Goal 13: Climate action	Only institutional collaboration	Forest Policy and Economics	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2011	107	8.23
76	The End of Religion? Examining the Role of Religiousness, Materialism, and Long-Term Orientation on Consumer Ethics in Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Journal of Business Ethics	Springer Nature	Arts and Humanities	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire: interviews	2014	107	10.70
77	Achieving sustainable competitive advantage through green entrepreneurial orientation and market orientation: The role of inter-organizational learning	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Bottom Line	Emerald Publishing	General Business, Management and Accounting	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	quantitative survey data	2019	107	21.40

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Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
78	Halal tourism: antecedent of tourist's satisfaction and word of mouth (WOM)	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	Only institutional collaboration	Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	Taylor & Francis	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: survey research	questionnaire	2018	107	17.83
79	Delocalizing Communities: Changing Forms of Community Engagement in Natural Resources Governance	Article	Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	in-depth exploration of multiple cases	2016	106	13.25
80	Descriptions of the lower limb skeleton of Homo floresiensis	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Journal of Human Evolution	Elsevier	Anthropology	Q1	Mixed Methods	Photographic Documentation; Quantitative Measurements; Morphological Analysis	2009	106	7.07
81	A survey of perception, knowledge, awareness, and attitude in regard to environmental problems in a sample of two different social groups in Jakarta, Indonesia	Article	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Environment, Development and Sustainability	Springer Nature	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	surveys, interviews	2001	105	4.57
82	The making of public Islam: Piety, agency, and commodification on the landscape of the Indonesian public sphere	Article	Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	Single authorship (no collaboration)	Contemporary Islam	Springer Nature	Religious Studies	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research; interviews; observation	2009	104	6.93
83	Decentralization Policy as Recentralization Strategy: Forest Management Units and Community Forestry in Indonesia	Article	Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	International collaboration	International Forestry Review	Commonwealth Forestry Association	Geography, Planning and Development	Q2	Qualitative: Narrative research	Semi-structured interviews; Secondary Data Research; Participant observation	2016	103	12.88
84	Oil Palm Boom, Contract Farming, and Rural Economic Development: Village-Level Evidence from Indonesia	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; group interviews; structured questionnaire	2017	103	14.71
85	Sacred forest, hunting, conservation in West Kalimantan, Indonesia	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	International collaboration	Human Ecology	Springer Nature	Anthropology	Q1	Qualitative: Ethnographic	interviews; observation	2004	102	5.10
86	Indonesian aquaculture futures: An analysis of fish supply and demand in Indonesia to 2030 and role of aquaculture using the AsiaFish model	Review	Goal 3: Good health and well-being	International collaboration	Marine Policy	Elsevier	Law	Q1	Mixed Methods	Secondary Data Research; group interviews; Quantitative alternative scenarios (Ass)	2017	102	14.57

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
87	Reconciling oil palm economic development and environmental conservation in Indonesia: A value chain dynamic approach	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Forest Policy and Economics	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	map the start of the value-added chain; conduct a field survey; evaluate findings and develop intervention scenarios	2020	102	25.50
88	Governance of flood risk management in a time of climate change: The cases of Jakarta and Rotterdam	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Environmental Politics	Taylor & Francis	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Secondary Data Research; group interviews	2013	102	9.27
89	Assessment of ecosystem services in homegarden systems in Indonesia, Sri Lanka, and Vietnam	Review	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Ecosystem Services	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2013	102	9.27
90	Sources of anthropogenic fire ignitions on the peat-swamp landscape in Kalimantan, Indonesia	Article	Goal 2: Zero hunger	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Secondary Data Research	2016	101	12.63
91	Virtual physics laboratory application based on the android smartphone to improve learning independence and conceptual understanding	Article	Goal 4: Quality education	Only institutional collaboration	International Journal of Instruction	Gate Association for Teaching and Education	Education	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	Surveys	2018	101	16.83
92	Regulating the oil palm boom: Assessing the effectiveness of environmental governance approaches to agro-industrial pollution in Indonesia	Article	Goal 7: Affordable and Clean Energy	International collaboration	Law and Policy	John Wiley & Sons	Law	Q2	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research; interviews; observation	2010	101	7.21
93	Rethinking Indonesia's Informal Sector	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Mixed Methods	quantitative survey data; small-scale qualitative survey; interviews	2016	101	12.63
94	Late Pleistocene Homo sapiens in a tropical rainforest fauna in East Java	Article	Goal 15: Life on land	International collaboration	Journal of Human Evolution	Elsevier	Anthropology	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Ekskavasi Arkeologis	2005	100	5.26
95	Limits and opportunities to community health worker empowerment: A multi-country comparative study	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Social Science and Medicine	Elsevier	History and Philosophy of Science	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research	2016	100	12.50
96	Continuities in stone flaking technology at Liang Bua, Flores, Indonesia	Article	Goal 17: Partnership for the goals	International collaboration	Journal of Human Evolution	Elsevier	Anthropology	Q1	Mixed Methods	observation; Ekskavasi Arkeologis	2009	100	6.67

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 1. One hundred most cited articles from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

Rank	Documents	Document type	Sustainable Development Goals mapped	Collaboration metrics	Source	Publisher	ASJC Category	Quartile Scopus	Research Method	Data Collection	Year Publish	Total Citations	Average citations per year
97	Upgrading for whom? Relationship coffee, value chain interventions and rural development in Indonesia	Article	Goal 10: Reduced inequalities	International collaboration	World Development	Elsevier	Sociology and Political Science	Q1	Qualitative: Multi Case Study	Secondary Data Research; group interviews	2018	99	16.50
98	The associations between environmental disclosures with financial performance, environmental performance, and firm value	Article	Goal 12: Responsible consumption and production	Only institutional collaboration	Social Responsibility Journal	Emerald Publishing	General Business, Management and Accounting	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	structural equation modelling; Secondary Data Research	2018	99	16.50
99	Measures that matter: an empirical investigation of intellectual capital and financial performance of banking firms in Indonesia	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	Only institutional collaboration	Journal of Intellectual Capital	Emerald Publishing	General Business, Management and Accounting	Q1	Quantitative: experimental research	surveys	2020	99	24.75
100	Perceptions across scales of governance and the Indonesian peatland fires	Article	Goal 8: Decent work and economic growth	International collaboration	Global Environmental Change	Elsevier	Geography, Planning and Development	Q1	Qualitative: Narrative research	Secondary Data Research; interviews	2017	99	14.14

Supplementary Table 2. Fifty-eight most cited sources of published research from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023

No.	Source	TP	TC	CPP	SNIP 2023
1	Advances in Health Sciences Education	1	131	131.0	2,147
2	Ageing and Society	1	197	197.0	1,547
3	Annals of Tourism Research	1	297	297.0	2,667
4	Aquaculture, Economics and Management	1	119	119.0	1,419
5	Asia Pacific Journal of Tourism Research	1	107	107.0	1,152
6	BMC Medical Education	1	284	284.0	1,603
7	Bottom Line	1	107	107.0	1,394
8	Building and Environment	2	386	193.0	2,022
9	Bulletin of Indonesian Economic Studies	2	261	130.5	2,743
10	Challenging The Secular State: The Islamization of Law in Modern Indonesia	1	124	124.0	NA
11	Cities	1	117	117.0	1,949
12	Comparative Political Studies	1	110	110.0	3,121
13	Contemporary Islam	1	104	104.0	1,494
14	Current Issues in Tourism	1	170	170.0	2,227
15	Economies	1	140	140.0	0.999
16	Ecosystem Services	2	229	114.5	1,808
17	Education and Information Technologies	1	169	169.0	2,308
18	Environment and Planning A	1	114	114.0	2,147
19	Environment, Development and Sustainability	1	105	105.0	1,297
20	Environmental Politics	1	102	102.0	2,665
21	Environmental Science and Policy	1	121	121.0	1,515
22	Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education	1	342	342.0	1,079
23	Food Policy	1	191	191.0	2,048
24	Forest Policy and Economics	5	608	121.6	1,384
25	Geoenvironmental Disasters	1	160	160.0	2,003
26	Global Environmental Change	6	798	133.0	2,605
27	Habitat International	3	438	146.0	1,908
28	Human Ecology	3	485	161.7	0.762
29	International Forestry Review	2	273	136.5	0.488
30	International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction	2	359	179.5	1,496
31	International Journal of Instruction	2	236	118.0	NA
32	International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research	1	140	140.0	0.544
33	International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research	1	109	109.0	NA
34	Islam and the State in Indonesia	1	120	120.0	NA
35	Journal of Agrarian Change	1	115	115.0	1,393
36	Journal of Business Ethics	1	107	107.0	2,841
37	Journal of Ethnic and Cultural Studies	1	377	377.0	0.943
38	Journal of Human Evolution	5	558	111.6	1,078
39	Journal of Intellectual Capital	1	99	99.0	2,341
40	Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity	3	555	185.0	1,646
41	Journal of Peasant Studies	2	285	142.5	3,037

(Continued)

Supplementary Table 2. Fifty-eight most cited sources of published research from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023 (Continued)

No.	Source	TP	TC	CPP	SNIP 2023
42	Journal of Sustainable Tourism	1	133	133.0	2,949
43	Journal of Turkish Science Education	1	113	113.0	0.921
44	Land Use Policy	5	656	131.2	1,894
45	Landscape and Urban Planning	1	205	205.0	2,187
46	Law and Policy	1	101	101.0	1,027
47	Marine Policy	2	283	141.5	1,292
48	Nature Climate Change	2	1205	602.5	5,887
49	Progress in Disaster Science	1	512	512.0	1,735
50	Quaternary Science Reviews	2	237	118.5	1,213
51	Review of Development Economics	1	114	114.0	0.990
52	Social Responsibility Journal	1	99	99.0	1,382
53	Social Science and Medicine	1	100	100.0	1,789
54	Sustainability (Switzerland)	2	249	124.5	1,086
55	Teaching and Teacher Education	1	148	148.0	2,467
56	Transportation	1	129	129.0	1,614
57	Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change	1	112	112.0	3,801
58	World Development	9	1207	134.1	2,412

TP= Total Papers, TC= Total Citations, SNIP= Source Normalized Impact per Paper (2023), CPP= Citations per paper

Supplementary Table 3. Seventeen most cited publishers in research from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations: 1999–2023

No.	Publisher	TP	TS	TC	CPP
1	Amazedia Solutions	1	1	109	109
2	Cambridge University Press	1	1	197	197
3	Commonwealth Forestry Association	2	1	273	136.50
4	Ekip Buro Makineleri A.S.	1	1	113	113
5	Elsevier	53	20	7893	7.45
6	Emerald Publishing	3	3	305	33.89
7	Florida Gulf Coast University	1	1	377	377
8	Gate Association for Teaching and Education	2	1	236	118
9	ISEAS / Ohio University Press	1	1	120	120
10	John Wiley & Sons	4	4	442	27.63
11	Modestum LTD	1	1	342	342
12	Multidisciplinary Digital Publishing Institute (MDPI)	4	3	501	41.75
13	SAGE	2	2	224	56
14	Society for Research and Knowledge Management Society for Research and Knowledge Management	1	1	140	140
15	Springer Nature	13	10	2879	22.15
16	Taylor & Francis	9	7	1177	18.68
17	University of Hawai'i Press	1	1	124	124

TP= Total Papers, TS= Total Sources, TC= Total Citations, CPP= Citations per paper

Supplementary Table 4. Twenty-one most frequent subject areas of research from Indonesia in social sciences by year of publication and total number of citations; 1999–2023

	ASJC Category	TP	%	TS	TC	CPP
1	Anthropology	6	6.12%	2	660	55.00
2	Archeology	3	3.06%	2	352	58.67
3	Arts and Humanities	2	2.04%	2	257	64.25
4	Cultural Studies	3	3.06%	2	662	110.33
5	Development	2	2.04%	2	243	60.75
6	Economics and Econometrics	2	2.04%	1	261	130.50
7	Economics, Econometrics and Finance	1	1.02%	1	140	140.00
8	Education	9	9.18%	8	1563	21.71
9	General Business, Management and Accounting	3	3.06%	3	305	33.89
10	General Economics, Econometrics and Finance	2	2.04%	1	250	125.00
11	Geography, Planning and Development	27	27.55%	15	3868	9.55
12	History and Philosophy of Science	1	1.02%	1	100	100.00
13	Law	3	3.06%	2	384	64.00
14	Management of Technology and Innovation	1	1.02%	1	109	109.00
15	Management, Monitoring, Policy and Law	3	3.06%	3	542	60.22
16	Public Health, Environmental and Occupational Health	1	1.02%	1	197	197.00
17	Religious Studies	1	1.02%	1	104	104.00
18	Social Sciences (miscellaneous)	2	2.04%	1	1205	602.50
19	Sociology and Political Science	21	21.43%	9	3101	16.41
20	Tourism, Leisure and Hospitality Management	2	2.04%	2	467	116.75
21	Urban Studies	3	3.06%	1	438	146.00